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Zinc(II) Complexes with some Substituted Thiourea

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NARDELLI and co-workers¹ have made an extensive study of complexes of urea, methyl urea, thioacetamide, thiourea with a number of metal ions and indicated² that the tendency of the metal to coordinate to the organic molecule decreases on passing from $SC(MH_2)_2$ to $SC(NMe_2)_2$ and more heavily substituted thiourea molecules. It was, therefore, thought worthwhile to study the complex formation with N-phenyl and Di-phenyl thiourea and this communication describes six compounds of the composition $[ZnL_2X_2]$ where L is N-Phenyl or N, N'-Diphenyl thiourea and X is Cl^- , Br^- or NCS^- .

0.001M acetone solution using Toshniwal's Conductivity Bridge. Infra-red spectra were recorded on Nujol mulls with a Unicam SP-200 Spectrophotometer. Relevant analytical, conductance and I. R. data are recorded in Table 1.

The six zinc complexes reported in the present investigation correspond to the composition $[ZnL_2X_2]$ from their analysis. These are white crystalline solids, have low melting points and are fairly soluble in acetone in which medium they are found to be non-electrolytes. Infrared spectra provide evidence for the bonding of the ligand to the metal since most of the ligand absorption bands are modified in the complexes. The assignment of absorption bands observed for the metal substituted thiourea complexes are as done by Olliff². From the infrared study in the range of 2-15 μ of methyl thiourea complexes of zinc, Quagliano and coworkers³ have noted that the metal is bonded through sulfur atom. Flint and Goodgame reported⁴ the for I. R. spectra of thiourea complexes of zinc and cadmium halides and showed complexes having the composition ML_2X_2 to be tetrahedral. In the case of the two thiocyanate complexes of zinc (II) in addition to the modified ligand absorption bands very sharp bands were observed at 2100 or 2080 cm^{-1} and $\sim 800 cm^{-1}$ region attributable to $\nu(C-N)$ and $\nu(C-S)$ respectively indicative of a N-bonded terminal thiocyanate. Hence the halide and thiocyanate complexes are four coordinated presumably having a tetrahedral environment around the metal ion. The sharp bands observed in the region $\sim 3200 cm^{-1}$ are undoubtedly assigned to the N-H stretching vibration and that at $\sim 1500 cm^{-1}$ correspond to the N-C-N stretching of the (B_1) type. The bands observed near about $\sim 730 cm^{-1}$ are assigned to the C-S stretching frequency. Bands around $\sim 1080 cm^{-1}$ are attributed to N-C-N bending vibrations.

TABLE I—ANALYSIS, MELTING POINT, CONDUCTANCE AND I. R. SPECTRAL DATA OF ZINC COMPLEXES

Compound	M.P. (°C.)	Conductance (mhos/cm ₂)	%Zinc		%Halogen or thiocyanate		I.R. Spectra (Cm. ⁻¹)			
			Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.	$\nu(C-S)$	N-C-N Bend	N-C-N Strength (B_1)	$\nu(N-H)$
ZnCl ₂ (N-Ph.tu) ₂	150	10.8	14.57	15.78	15.75	16.05	730s	1085s	1495br	3200s
ZnBr ₂ (N-Ph.tu) ₂	175	6.8	12.06	12.30	30.58	30.08	735s	1080s	1490br	3180s
Zn(NCS) ₂ (N-Ph.tu) ₂	147	9.6	13.23	13.42	23.63	23.80	740s	1085s	1495s	3200s
ZnCl ₂ (Diph.tu) ₂	185	8.1	10.75	10.96	11.65	11.91	725s	1080s	1500br	3250s
ZnBr ₂ (Diph.tu) ₂	159	9.4	9.95	9.83	23.92	24.03	730s	1075s	1500br	3200s
Zn(NCS) ₂ (Diph.tu) ₂	135	9.9	10.04	10.19	17.84	18.08	725s	1080s	1505s	3250s

Ph.tr—Phenyl thiourea

Ethanol solution of zinc chloride, bromide and thiocyanate (20 ml) were treated with ethanolic solution of substituted thiourea in 1:2 ratio separately and the solution refluxed for one hour. Then 10 ml CCl_4 was added to each of the reaction mixtures and refluxing continued for three hours. The resulting clear solution was kept for two to three days after addition of 5 ml more of CCl_4 . White crystalline compounds separated out. The compounds were suction filtered, washed with ethanol, followed by ether and dried *in vacuo*. Metal and halogen or thiocyanate were estimated by standard methods after alkali fusion (for anions only). Conductance was measured in

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